

Development of a tricomponent composite graphene oxide-chitosan-hydroxyapatite for bone tissue engineering

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Abstract : The hydroxyapatite (HAP) was isolated from the bones of the Catla fish (*Catla catla*) by thermal calcinations at 400 °C, 600 °C, 800 °C and 900 °C. Among them the optimum temperature was found to be 800 °C. The graphite (GP) was converted into graphene oxide (GO) and tricomponent composite of GO-chitosan-HAP was prepared. The tricomponent composite was characterized by thermogravimetric (TG) and differential thermogravimetric (DTG) analysis, Fourier Transformed Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The compressive and tensile strength of the composite was found to be 9.77 ± 1.47 MPa and 0.650 ± 0.276 MPa respectively. The compressive strength exhibited by the tricomponent composite met the requirement for bone tissue engineering (3–10 MPa).

Keywords : Hydroxyapatite, chitosan, graphene oxide, composite.

Introduction

The basic requirements for bone tissue engineering include cell adhesion, differentiation and proliferation, non-cytotoxicity and osteoconductivity to biomimic the structure of natural human bone¹. Hydroxyapatite (HAP) has many of them and hence used widely as an important component in bone tissue engineering.

HAP can either be synthesized in the laboratory by chemical method or isolated from natural source. *Catla catla* is a common fish found in the rivers and lakes of India. The major waste (70–85%) from the fish processing industries including skin, viscera, scales, bones and bone frames are either dumped in land or hauled in the oceans causing environmental problems. The isolation of HAP from the bone of Catla fish will not only give value addition but also can solve the environmental problem due to dumping. The major drawbacks in using HAP for major load bearing applications are the poor mechanical strength and brittleness^{2,3}. Recently, several HAP-polymer composites with increased mechanical strength have been developed and reported for orthopaedic applications. Chitosan is one of the natural polysaccharides used for several biomedical applications including bone tissue engineering. The mechanical strength of chitosan-HAP com-

posite can be further improved by the incorporation of graphene oxide (GO). GO exhibits high reactivity, biocompatibility and biostability due to the higher amount of oxygen groups⁴. Hence, the composite of GO-chitosan-HAP was developed for bone tissue engineering applications.

Experimental

Materials :

Chitosan powder (degree of deacetylation 90% with molecular weight 310 kDa) was purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries Ltd., Japan. HAP was isolated from Catla fish bones (purchased from a local fish market). GP was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. AR grade NaOH, conc. H₂SO₄, NaNO₃, KMnO₄, H₂O₂ and HCl were purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals.

Isolation of HAP :

Catla fish bones were washed with NaOH solution and rinsed with water to remove the excess skin and meat. Then the bones were dried in hot air oven at 100 °C and grained in to powder. The powder thus obtained was placed in open silica crucible and calcined in a previously heated electric furnace (INDFUR, India) at 400 °C, 600 °C, 800 °C and 900 °C with 8 h holding time².

Synthesis of GO :

GO was synthesized from GP by Hummer's method⁵.

Preparation of GO-chitosan-HAP composite :

4.037 g of chitosan (degree of deacetylation 90% with molecular weight 310 kDa) in 400 ml of 2% acetic acid solution was added to the 120 mg of GO dispersed in water and the mixture was kept under stirring for 3 h. To the GO-chitosan solution the HAP (9.7 g) dispersed in water was slowly added and then stirred for 24 h. Further, it was neutralized with 10% NaOH (AR grade) and finally washed with water and filtered⁶.

Characterization :

The thermal stability of the composite was studied using TG and DTA (SDTQ 600 TA Instrument, USA) analysis with scan range of 50 °C to 800 °C at constant heating rate of 10 °C/min in the presence of nitrogen atmosphere. The FTIR (Jasco FTIR 4100, Japan) spectrum was recorded within the range of 4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} . The phase and crystallinity of the samples were examined by XRD (Bruker, D8 Advance X-ray Diffraction spectrophotometer, German) at room temperature using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ as the radiation and 1.504 Å wavelength, over the angle range 10° to 80°, step size 0.02° and scan speed 0.5°/min. The resultant XRD values for isolated HAP were compared with the standard Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) cards available in the system software.

Mechanical strength :

The wet composite material was molded into cylindrical columns and rectangular slabs and dried in air at room temperature. Four cylindrical columns with cross sectional area 104.66 mm^2 , 94.44 mm^2 , 108.12 mm^2 , and 112.45 mm^2 and four rectangular slabs with dimensions 16.9 mm × 9.0 mm × 3.35 mm, 16.9 mm × 12.0 mm × 1.86 mm, 21.4 mm × 9.7 mm × 3.23 mm and 15.9 mm × 11.9 mm × 3.38 mm were used for the study of compressive and tensile strength. The tests were performed using the system Tinius Olsen, Model H5KS, UK. The 5000 N load cell with the standard grips of crosshead speed of 0.5 mm min^{-1} was used for the compression and tensile strength measurements⁷.

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

The XRD pattern of HAP isolated below 600 °C shows

the removal of organic matter was incomplete but XRD values of HAP isolated by calcinations above 600 °C were in good conformity with the standard HAP (JCPDS-09-0432/1996) indicating the complete removal of organic matter. Further, the calcinations above 600 °C showed sharpening of peaks for HAP. This indicate that the crystalline nature of HAP increase with the increase in temperature. Moreover, the size of crystals formed by calcinations above 800 °C was smaller than the HAP got by the calcination below 800 °C. Hence, the temperature of calcinations for the isolation of HAP was fixed as 800 °C. The *d*-spacing line, 2θ angle, relative intensity of the characteristic peaks, lattice parameters (*a* and *c*) and the unit cell volume (*v*) of isolated HAP at 600 °C, 800 °C and 900 °C were found to be in very good conformity with the standard values (JCPDS-09-0432/1996)^{2,3}.

The conversion of graphite to GO was confirmed by the appearance of a high intensity peak at 10.5° with a *d*-spacing line of 0.705 nm higher than that of graphite (GP). This increase in *d*-spacing is due to the presence of oxygen containing groups in the GO structure⁴.

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of the GO-chitosan-HAP composite and raw materials. All characteristic peaks of chitosan, GO and HAP are in good agreement with the values reported in literature^{4,6,8}. The XRD pattern of composite showed low intense peaks of chitosan and GO along with peaks of HAP with a slight shift. This confirmed the presence of all the components as well as the formation of the tricomponent composite^{4,8}.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of chitosan, GO, HAP and composite.

FTIR and thermal stability :

The FTIR spectra of raw bone and HAP isolated at 400 °C and 600 °C showed amide peak at approximately 1650 cm^{-1} indicating the incomplete removal of organic

matters. The HAP isolated at 800 °C and 900 °C showed all the characteristic peaks of HAP as reported in the literature^{2,3}. Further, the oxidation of GP to GO was confirmed by the peaks at 3552 cm⁻¹ ν(-OH), 1726 cm⁻¹ ν(C=O), 1224 cm⁻¹ ν(C-OH) and 1051 cm⁻¹ ν(C-O-C)³.

Fig. 2(A) shows the FTIR spectrum of the GO-chitosan-HAP composite and raw materials. All the characteristic peaks of chitosan, GO and HAP are in good conformity with the literature values^{4,9}. Appearance of a new peak at 1658 cm⁻¹ with lower intensity may be attributed to amide formation as a result of the reaction between -COOH group of GO with the -NH₂ group of chitosan^{6,8}.

The TG/DTA analysis for the composite material is shown in Fig. 2B. The weight loss observed in the temperature range of 268–382 °C is attributed to the decomposition of the chitosan molecule. This is further supported by the endothermic peak at 314 °C and 357 °C in DTA chitosan. The lowering of weight loss above 600 °C indicated the GO-chitosan-HAP composite gain thermal stability above 600 °C⁶.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of chitosan, GO, HAP and composite (A) and TG/DTA images of composite (B).

Compressive and tensile strength :

The compressive and tensile strength results are shown in Fig. 3. Compressive and tensile strength of the composite was found to be 9.77 ± 1.47 MPa and 0.650 ± 0.276 MPa respectively. These values meet the requirements for bone tissue engineering. The multiple breaks observed in tensile strength curve may be due to layered structure of the composite material⁷.

The higher compressive and tensile strength observed may be due to the strong interactions between the GO, chitosan and HAP.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength (A) and tensile strength (B) images of GO-chitosan-HAP composite.

Conclusion

A new composite of GO-chitosan-natural HAP isolated from Catla fish bone was prepared as a scaffold. XRD and FT-IR analysis confirmed the formation of the composite. The compressive strength of 9.77 ± 1.47 MPa for the prepared composite meets the requirements for bone tissue engineering (3–10 MPa).

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